

A Machine Learning Interpretation of the Correlation Between Poverty and Air Pollution in the Contiguous United States

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Abstract

The correlation between poverty and air pollution in the contiguous United States is a widely debated issue, often suggesting that impoverished areas suffer higher pollution levels due to socioeconomic disparities. However, existing studies frequently lack the integration of advanced analytical techniques and fail to account for a comprehensive range of variables. This research paper addresses these gaps by employing sophisticated machine learning models to analyze an extensive dataset encompassing various socioeconomic and environmental metrics. Utilizing linear regression, decision trees, and neural networks, we rigorously examined the data. While the variables were able to predict county-wide poverty rates to reasonably low RMSE and MAE values, our results indicate no significant correlation between poverty levels alone with air pollution indices. The latter finding challenges conventional understanding and highlights the complexity of the relationship between socioeconomic status and environmental quality. By offering a data-driven perspective, our study encourages policymakers to reconsider the factors influencing environmental justice and to look beyond economic status alone. Our work underscores the necessity for further investigation into other potential determinants of pollution, contributing to the discourse on environmental equity. This research provides a fresh, nuanced view that questions established beliefs and underscores the multifaceted nature of socioeconomic-environmental interactions.

Keywords: Air Pollution, Environmental Justice, Socioeconomic Status, Demographics, Machine Learning, United States

I. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between poverty and environmental quality has long been a central topic in the field of environmental justice. The premise that poorer communities are disproportionately affected by pollution is grounded in a significant body of literature suggesting that these areas face higher exposure to environmental hazards, limited access to clean resources, and adverse health outcomes. This study aims to delve deeper into this complex issue, critically analyzing the existing literature and employing advanced machine learning techniques to provide a nuanced understanding of the correlation between poverty and air pollution in the contiguous United States.

Environmental justice advocates argue that low-income communities are more likely to be situated near sources of air pollution, such as industrial plants, landfills, and highways, leading to heightened exposure to harmful air pollutants [1], [2]. This exposure is believed to contribute to a range of health problems, including respiratory diseases, cardiovascular conditions, and cancer [3]. Furthermore, these communities often lack the political clout and resources to effectively combat or mitigate the impacts of environmental degradation [4]. The concept of environmental racism has been used to describe the systemic nature of these injustices, where minority communities are disproportionately burdened by environmental hazards [5].

The implications of this problem are profound. Health disparities driven by environmental pollution can exacerbate existing socioeconomic inequalities, trapping communities in cycles of poverty and poor health. Children in these areas, exposed to pollutants like lead and particulate matter, can experience developmental issues and decreased academic performance, which in turn affect their future economic opportunities [6]. Adults may face

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increased healthcare costs and lost productivity due to air pollution-related illnesses, further straining limited financial resources [7].

Moreover, the geographic clustering of air pollution in low-income areas can depress property values and deter investment, perpetuating economic decline and reducing the overall quality of life [8]. This spatial dimension of environmental injustice not only affects the physical health of residents but also their social and economic wellbeing, creating a multifaceted problem that demands comprehensive solutions.

While the argument for a link between poverty and pollution is compelling, existing studies often suffer from several methodological limitations. First, many rely on cross-sectional data that capture a single point in time, failing to account for temporal variations and long-term trends [9]. This approach can miss dynamic changes in pollution levels and socioeconomic status, leading to static and potentially misleading conclusions.

Second, the spatial resolution of the data used in these studies is often coarse, which can obscure localized variations and lead to inaccurate conclusions [10]. Fine-grained data is essential to capture the true exposure levels experienced by communities and to identify air pollution hotspots that might be overlooked in broader analyses. However, obtaining and integrating such detailed data presents significant challenges, including issues of data availability, quality, and consistency.

Third, conventional statistical methods employed in these studies may not adequately control for confounding variables, such as population density, industrial activity, and regulatory policies, which can influence both poverty and air pollution levels [8]. These factors are crucial in understanding the complex interactions between socioeconomic conditions and environmental quality. For instance, areas with high industrial activity may have higher air pollution levels regardless of the economic status of residents, while stringent regulatory policies might mitigate air pollution even in poorer areas.

Moreover, much of the existing literature employs simplistic measures of both poverty and pollution. Poverty is often assessed using income levels alone, without considering other dimensions such as education, employment, and housing quality [11]. This narrow focus can overlook important aspects of socioeconomic deprivation that influence vulnerability to pollution. Similarly, pollution is frequently measured using a limited set of indicators, such as air quality indices or proximity to hazardous sites, which do not capture the full spectrum of environmental risks [12]. Comprehensive measures that include various pollutants and exposure pathways are necessary to fully understand the environmental burden on communities.

Finally, there is a tendency in the literature to generalize findings across different geographic and socio-economic contexts, which can obscure important local variations and lead to policy recommendations that are not universally applicable [13]. The diversity of environmental and social conditions across the United States necessitates localized studies that can inform targeted interventions and policies.

This study aims to address these gaps by leveraging advanced machine learning techniques to analyze a robust dataset encompassing a wide range of socioeconomic and environmental variables. By using methods such as linear regression, decision trees, and neural networks, we provide a more nuanced analysis that accounts for complex interactions and confounding factors. Our goal is to offer a data-driven perspective on the relationship between poverty and pollution, contributing to the ongoing discourse on environmental justice and informing policymakers on the factors influencing environmental equity.

II. METHODS

A. Dataset & Preprocessing (Poverty Prediction)

This paper utilized data from the United States Social Vulnerability Index (US SVI) database, which contains economic and demographic information collected from every county in the contiguous United States. The database, compiled in 2022, was used for determining the Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) of a region, this value, a combination of weighted sums of its 16 contributor variables, helps to determine the United States counties most vulnerable towards life-threatening disasters including wildfires, epidemics, and nuclear meltdowns. Each of the data's features also includes a confidence interval, representing the range of error for values; however, for this study, only the estimated values are utilized. To ensure consistency and objective model training results, all data was retrieved as percentages of the total population. In total, 15 inputs are used to predict county-wide poverty rates. The dataset was subsequently preprocessed, with null data values imputed using a k -Nearest Neighbors strategy, ensuring consistency between similar data points.

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Given the absence of minimal number of features, along with the complexity of accounting for factor-poverty contributions, the dataset was expanded to every polynomial and interaction feature up to a degree of 2, allowing machine learning models to better interpret relationships between features. For instance, with two features, x and y , the degree 2 transformation creates features x, y, xy, x^2 , and y^2 . Using this approach, the number of features expanded from 15 to 136 features.

The data's skew was then analyzed, with values having various degrees of skew, providing impractical data towards the regression models. For all input features beyond a moderately high skew, or around an absolute value of 0.5, a Yeo-Johnson power transformation, shown below, is applied [14].

$$x = \begin{cases} \frac{(x+1)^\lambda - 1}{\lambda} & x \geq 0, \lambda \neq 0; \\ \log(x+1) & x \geq 0, \lambda = 0; \\ -\frac{(-x+1)^{2-\lambda} - 1}{2-\lambda} & x < 0, \lambda \neq 2; \\ -\log(-x+1) & x < 0, \lambda = 2; \end{cases}$$

The above piecewise function, where x is the input value and λ is the power transformation, preserves the rank order of data, effectively maintaining data integrity even after the shift. It is important to note that for the equation, the functions at $x < 0, \lambda = 2$ and $x \geq 0, \lambda = 0$ are derived as the limit of their corresponding power functions ($x < 0, \lambda \neq 2$ and $x \geq 0, \lambda \neq 0$, respectively) converges with λ . Additionally, the inclusion of the $+1$ constant absent in the Box-Cox transformation [15] permits the data transformation to be an identity transformation at $\lambda = 1$, effectively allowing any range of values to be transformed.

After addressing dataset skew, a Lasso regularization was applied to reduce input dimensionality. This L1 regularization's objective function shrinks various feature coefficients to zero, nullifying any contribution of those features. With a tuned Lasso regularization strength of 0.0025, the final feature set contained 37 features, only three of which were primitive: "EP_UNEMP", "EP_HBURD", and "EP_UNINSUR", corresponding to the percentage of unemployed civilians older than age 16, housing cost-burdened families, and uninsured population, respectively. Other percentage features, such as elderly population and zero-vehicle households, were present within interaction features.

B. Dataset & Preprocessing (Pollution Prediction)

Following the complete understanding of pollution factors and prevalences, the question is proposed: can a machine learning model accurately use poverty rates to predict pollution data?

The dataset that contains pollution information is the United States Environmental Justice Index, a compilation of data from the U.S. Census Bureau (US CB), U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), U.S. Mine Safety and Health Administration (US MSHA), and U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (US CDC). Each of these government organizations compile varying metrics on community-wide demographic, economic, and environmental concerns. The original dataset consists of data in terms of each census tract in the United States, designated by the US CB, and contains a population roughly from 1,200 to 8,000 [16], with various tracts exceeding these boundaries. The features selected for pollution analysis are "E_OZONE", "E_PM", and "E_DSLPM", corresponding to the average days above ozone regulatory standard, average days above $PM_{2.5}$ regulatory standard, and ambient diesel concentration (in PM/m^3). All feature data was obtained through the US EPA's National Environmental Health Tracking Network from 2014 to 2016. Because the US SVI dataset utilizes state counties rather than census tracts, weighted sums of every census tract must be taken in order to obtain a generalized data. For all pollution metrics, the census tracts were weighted based on their population size ("E_TOTPOP"), the weight for every tract was summed together, and was subsequently divided by the total population of the county (summation of all census tract populations).

Through this approach, data from 3,100 counties were obtained, with a k-Nearest Neighbors imputer filling in the data for the remaining 9 counties.

Thus, the dataset containing county-wide data was retrieved. The resulting input was "EP_POV150"- the percentage of poverty below 150%- and the outputs were "E_OZONE", "E_PM25", "E_DSLPM". Due to every output containing levels of skew, a Box-Cox transformation synonymous to the one applied to poverty rate was applied to the output, with "EP_POV150" retaining its previous transformation. The lambda values for all three outputs are -2.636, 2.091, and -3.540, respectively, reducing their absolute skews from ≥ 0.50 to ≤ 0.50 . Due to a singular input being fitted onto the data, excessively complex models were not tested, as it would both generalize

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poorly to the data and increase training time, two caveats crucial for our models. Thus, the Cubist, Multi-Layered Perceptron, and CatBoost models were removed, and the Adaptive Boosting and Elastic Net models were used; the final regression models for this task were Linear Regression, Stochastic Gradient Descent, Adaptive Boosting, and Elastic Net.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Pollution

In order to appropriately visualize state-wide pollution data across the United States, the metrics across each state were averaged for each of the state's counties and plotted through QGIS, illustrated below (Figs. 1-3). For all metrics, a higher duration of presence (for Ozone and $PM_{2.5}$) or a higher concentration (for Diesel), can be associated with a more polluted state.

Fig. 1- Mean days with excess ozone across the contiguous United States.

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Fig. 2- Mean days with excess PM_{2.5} across the contiguous United States.

Fig. 3- Mean diesel concentration across the contiguous United States.

For all pollution metrics above, the United States West Coast and East Coast consistently held sustained pollution concentrations. The Central United States, on the other hand, held the lowest results for PM_{2.5} and Diesel Concentration, while performing poorer towards Ozone data. It can also be shown that Northern states, particularly in the Western half of the nation, carry lower pollution concentrations than Southern states. It can also be shown that there is no absolute correlation between the various pollution metrics across the United States.

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In order to holistically understand the general pollutant patterns, a literature review on the impact of past socio-environmental legislation was conducted. Specifically, the states in question include California, Florida, Indiana, and Utah. To ensure appropriate interpretation, the literature review contains legislation only from January 1st, 1999 to December 31st, 2016 (the conclusion of data collection),

i) California

A study by Propper et al. [17] analyzed the concentration of seven California-borne toxic air pollutants from 1999-2012. Through data analysis of day-to-day pollution metrics, they discovered that, despite population seeing an uptick of almost one-third (31%) and increased long-distance hauls of well over two-thirds (81%), ambient diesel concentration decreased by nearly two-thirds (68%), attributing to the lack of empirical correlation between these immediate factors. Other TACs, such as Benzene and Formaldehyde, also saw decreases in concentration, albeit to a lower degree (~20%). The cause, as speculated by the authors, was the result of increased vehicle regulatory standards, such as the 2008 California Statewide Truck and Bus Rule proposed 8 years prior [18], requiring heavy-duty vehicles and buses to meet 2010 diesel emission regulation standards. While the ambient diesel concentrations, depicted on the map, still shows California in the fourth quartile of emissions, the number is extremely reasonable when accounting for the industrial significance of the state; however, this regulation unsuccessfully addressed the industries themselves, which saw some of the highest days above ozone regulation in the nation.

ii) Florida

On the other hand, Florida saw mean days with excess ozone in the lower quartiles of the states, despite having some of the highest population density in cities including Miami and Hialeah. While intuitively the opposite, population density, has been found to hold a strong negative correlation with sustained ozone concentrations [19]; that, along with the strict regulations on vehicular and industrial NO_x [20] has proven extremely effective towards diminishing the consequences of Chapman's cycle, namely the absence of the ozone dissolution step that results in accumulating ozone concentrations. Beyond ozone concentrations, NO_x has been proven to insinuate respiratory irritation in abiotic species [21], decreasing the productivity of cities. However, even with low mean days above ozone levels and average mean days with excess PM_{2.5}, the diesel concentration stands as an outlier. While Florida, similar to California, stands as a hub of domestic commerce, its legislation-backed rapid population growth since 1999 [22] has served to offset regulatory measures.

iii) Indiana

Given all three pollutants remained at a fairly high level, Indiana serves as a hallmark for investigation. A 2019 study by Dietrich et al. [23] measured the presence of various PM within roadways in Gary, Indiana, correlating their findings to the steel and coal plants operating in regions' past years. In particular, they determined that Zinc, Chromium, and Vanadium, three heavy-metals proven to be primary pollutants, have roadway measures of up to 484.4, 605.0, and 177.4 ppm, respectively, well above the regulatory standards. The city, from 2015 census reports conducted by the U.S. Department of Commerce [24], saw 84.8% of its nearly 80,000 population being black alone, with 38.7% of the population living in poverty, two prominent factors that correlate to pollution. Thus, a high correlation between minority groups, poverty rates, and pollution could exist, which wasn't proven by poverty rates alone in this study.

iv) Utah

A literature review by Ou et al. [25] cited that Utah's variant thermal inversion and pollution emissions creates large variabilities between pollution metrics, although it has cut emissions by one-third (38%) between 2005-2020. In another study on PM₁₀ and daily mortality rates in Utah County from 1985 to 1989. The researchers concluded that, by isolating all other TACs, an increase of PM₁₀ levels of 100 µg/m² resulted, on average, in 16% increased mortality. While PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} do hold fundamental differences, namely in particulate size and composition, their impact towards humans do hold some similarities [26]. This conclusion is supported by Utah's mountainous geography, particularly in inland regions such as Salt Lake City, which result in thermal inversions that incubate PM_{2.5}. However, Utah sits in the lower quartiles of days with excess PM_{2.5} with 5.826 days, most likely attributed to the indiscriminate averaging of inter-county pollution metrics, omitting information such as Utah's population centroid in the Wasatch Front. Other factors like ozone, which generally remain consistent through the state, have been exacerbated by recent decades' urbanization to Utah's largest counties.

B. Poverty Prediction

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In total, five machine learning models were tested: Cubist, Multi-Layered Perceptron, CatBoost, Linear Regression, and Stochastic Gradient Descent. These models were selected based on their varying purposes, from the simplicity of the linear regression to the rule-based potential of Quinlan’s Cubist implementation. Three evaluation metrics were also tested: R^2 , RMSE, and MAE. R^2 , or the correlation of determination, represents the explained variance, or strength, of model predictions. RMSE and MAE represent the amount of model error, where MAE is the mean error of all prediction samples and RMSE is the degree of error derived from mean squared error (MSE), resulting in sensitivity to outliers. For RMSE, this means that the relative difference from the MAE represents the degree to which outliers are present in the prediction. Ideally, for all models, RMSE should be tuned to convergence with MAE.

Given the output poverty rates have undergone a Box-Cox transformation, the scoring functions used must perform an inverse result transformation, in order to ensure predictions are consistent with the original data. Through a 5-fold cross validation prediction, the entire training set was predicted, and its R^2 , RMSE, and MAE values were retrieved and analyzed (Table 1).

Table-1: County-wide poverty rate model training results.

Model	R^2	RMSE	MAE
Cubist	0.736	4.284	3.070
MLP Regression	0.680	4.717	3.279
CatBoost	0.755	4.128	2.947
Linear Regression	0.736	4.288	3.126
SGD Regression	0.728	4.349	3.159

The results show that, despite a lower coefficient of determination, the model performs reasonably well on the data, achieving a mean absolute error of only 2.947 for the top model, corresponding to 2.947%. The model strengths, dictated primarily by RMSE and MAE values, are as follows, in descending order: CatBoost, Cubist, Linear Regression, SGD Regression, and MLP Regression. The RMSE, while reasonably within range of the MAE (~1 unit difference), does illustrate the prevalence of outliers within the model. Thus, a test set evaluation was conducted, and its values plotted (Fig. 4), affirming the RMSE and MAE relationships.

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Fig. 4- Test set predicted versus expected poverty prevalences for all models.

The test set, while containing some outliers particularly present in higher poverty rates ($> 50\%$), is able to cluster data within the 10-30% poverty range. The predicted set of outliers, interestingly, is most prominent in the CatBoost model in the ranges of 40-60%, despite the model holding both the lowest MAE and RMSE, a fact attributed to its strong predictive ability towards clustered data. Additionally, the linear regression, given the context of this task, performed surprisingly well, even better than the neural network and its linear boosting counterpart Stochastic Gradient Descent. This proves that the data can also be represented well simplistically, as the scale of weights and biases could cause overfitting among the training data.

The CatBoost regression model, first proposed by Prokhorenkova et. al in 2018 [27], builds upon the gradient boosting model's error of prediction shifts- the influence of training data towards validation data- causing overfitting between the training and validation performance curves; this principle is also known as "target leakage". CatBoost, thus, utilizes permutative ordered boosting to accurately process categorical data and mitigate target leakage. In addition, the model derives symmetric trees, where each node can be split using bitwise operators. Hence, this approach results in far faster model training times compared to its gradient boosting counterpart. In fact, its model simplicity through symmetrical trees likely allowed CatBoost to retrieve more generalizable feature relationships; permitting its higher performance than that of other models.

Given this data represents counties across the United States- with varying standards of living, socio-economic statuses, and geographical and environmental factors, all of which create outliers or discrepancies in poverty predictions- the lower R^2 value is justified. The report on poverty rates also helps to show the power of feature expansion by creating polynomial and interaction features, allowing the model to generalize to unseen data. The dataset's inclusion of these extended features, many of which weren't selected for their individual importance, proves that a re-interpretation of its values allows it to gain importance. This approach was also attributed to the

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strong performance of the linear model, which generally performs poorly towards individual, non-interaction, features, as it omits the step of the model attempting to determine underlying feature interactions within its algorithms, much of which cannot be found otherwise.

C. Pollution Prediction

Similar to the poverty prediction previous models, these four models underwent a 5-fold cross validation prediction before being evaluated, ensuring the entire training dataset was analyzed. For all three outputs, the model results were aggregated and analyzed (Tables 2-4).

Table-2: Model predictions of county-wide ozone concentration days above regulation.

Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE
Linear Regression	-0.028	2.123	0.540
SGDRegressor	-0.036	2.131	0.550
AdaBoostRegressor	-0.025	2.120	0.545
Elastic Net	-0.035	2.130	0.554

Table-3: Model predictions of county-wide PM_{2.5} concentration days above regulation.

Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE
Linear Regression	0.001	1.601	1.272
SGDRegressor	-0.017	1.616	1.263
AdaBoostRegressor	-0.018	1.617	1.301
Elastic Net	-0.002	1.604	1.282

Table-4: Model predictions of county-wide diesel concentration.

Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE
Linear Regression	0.001	0.135	0.093
SGDRegressor	-0.143	0.145	0.101
AdaBoostRegressor	-0.007	0.136	0.093
Elastic Net	-0.040	0.138	0.095

For all evaluation metrics, the coefficient of determination oscillated around 0 for every model, attesting to the lack of correlation between the poverty rate alone to pollution. Interestingly, the RMSE value for the models, which penalizes larger errors to a greater extent, is far larger relative to MAE for Ozone than for PM_{2.5} or Diesel Concentration predictions. This is attributed to the larger exhibited errors in the prediction of mean days above Ozone standard. No model proved to be stronger than the other models for a pollution metric, aside from Stochastic Gradient Descent achieving an R² absolute difference of 0.128 compared to the averages of the other three regressors, despite performing relatively similar in RMSE or MAE, which is likely attributed to its poorer prediction towards clustered groups of data. Despite the potency of Elastic Net regression in numerous other applications, combining both Lasso (L1) and Ridge (L2) techniques, the sole lack of training data resulted in negligible regularization effects, performing nearly synonymous with the Linear Regression in all tests. Additionally, the only boosting model, AdaBoost, often used for its versatility towards both simplistic and complex tasks, performed similarly due to the lack of correlative data. In addition, taking the pairwise correlation between poverty rates and the three outputs provides the values of -0.091, 0.098, and -0.021 for Ozone, PM_{2.5}, and Diesel predictions. While these values only represent the strength of correlation between two variables, they further prove the difficulty to represent pollution through solely poverty.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the relationship between poverty and pollution in the contiguous United States using advanced machine learning techniques on a comprehensive dataset. Contrary to the prevailing assumption of a direct correlation, our findings indicate no significant relationship between poverty levels and pollution indices. This suggests that the interaction between socioeconomic status and environmental quality is more complex than previously understood, with other factors like industrial activity, regulatory policies, and community resilience

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playing more significant roles. By highlighting the methodological limitations of existing research and employing sophisticated analytical methods, we provide a nuanced perspective that challenges established beliefs. Our findings underscore the need for policymakers to consider a broader range of factors when addressing environmental justice and to develop targeted strategies informed by comprehensive, data-driven analyses.

DATA AVAILABILITY

This paper utilized data from the United States Social Vulnerability Index (US SVI) database

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